

FACULTY EMPOWERMENT STRATEGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The cycle of activities starting with planning of human resources, recruitment, performance appraisal and professional development programmes, feedback and analysis all ensure that they are utilized to develop strategies to upgrade the professional competence of the staff through various mechanisms evolved. In higher education institutions efforts are continuously made to enhance the professional development of teaching and non teaching staff, through strategies for empowerment includes training, retraining and motivating the employees for the roles and responsibility they perform. It is necessary to have a performance appraisal system comprehensive enough to ensure that information on multiple activities is appropriately captured and considered for better appraisal. The outcome of the review of the performance appraisal is development of efficiency and transparency in fulfilling the aspirations of the stake holders and greater commitment to teaching-learning process. In this paper, we have identified various faculty empowerment strategies to be adopted for future quality improvement in higher education institutions in the light of a comprehensive performance management system based on 360° appraisal.

Keywords: Faculty empowerment strategy, Quality in higher education, 360° faculty appraisal.

Introduction:

One of the important resources in providing quality in higher education system is human resources. This include innovative administrators, effective teaching staff and efficient non-teaching staff. Any organization which identifies, utilizes and develops such resources for its growth can become successful in providing sustainable quality education [Harvey, L. (1998), Harman, G. (1998) and Mukhopadhyay, M. (2005)]. The process of planning human resources including recruitment, performance appraisal and planning professional development programmes and seeking appropriate feedback, analysis of responses and ensure that they form the basis for planning. The cycle of activities starting with planning of human resources, recruitment, performance appraisal and professional development programmes, feedback and analysis all ensure that they are utilized to develop strategies to upgrade the professional competence of the staff through various mechanisms evolved. In higher education institutions efforts are continuously made to enhance the professional development of teaching and non teaching staff, through strategies for empowerment includes training, retraining and motivating the employees for the roles and responsibility they perform. It is necessary to have a performance appraisal system comprehensive enough to ensure that information on multiple activities is appropriately captured and considered for better appraisal [Aithal P. S. & Suresh Kumar, (2015)]. The outcome of the review of the performance appraisal is development of efficiency and transparency in fulfilling the aspirations of the stake holders and greater commitment to teaching-learning process. Efforts are made to upgrade the professional competence of the staff. There are mechanisms evolved for regular performance appraisal of staff. In this paper, we have identified various faculty empowerment strategies to be adopted for future quality improvement in higher education institutions in the light of a comprehensive performance management system based on 360° appraisal [Rogers D. L. (2000), Paul et. al. (2005) Sanjaya Mishra (2007)].

Efforts made by the Institution to Enhance the Professional Development of its Teaching and Non-teaching Staff:

The following efforts are made by the institution to enhance the professional development of its teaching and non teachingstaff :

- A. The Institution believes in value-based, culture oriented and quality education. Every year the institution organise various programmes such as Conferences, workshops, Faculty Development Programmes, Seminars, etc. in which the faculty are actively involved.
- B. Encouragement to attend seminars, conferences, workshops, faculty development programmesorganised by other institutions.
- C. Encouragement to take up research projects in various fields of interest.

D. Institution encourages the staff to become members of professional bodies and participate in their programs.

E. Training programmes areorganised for non-teaching staff such as computer proficiency and use of technology in their respective field of work. They are also motivated and encouraged to take up higher education in the field of their interest and required support from the institution is extended for the same.

F. The college encourages its faculty to publish at least two research papers every year. The idea and plan for these papers are evolved in programs conducted in the college like Manegma.

G. The young faculty members are encouraged to register for M.Phil./Ph.D. with a reasonable time frame. Some of faculty members are already doing Ph.D. under the supervision of the head of the Institute.

H. The college improves the competence of the faculty in their own subjects by preparing the study materials on their own. This is used as course material by students in the subjects taught by them.

Strategies Adopted by the Institution for Faculty Empowerment:

In order help the employees perform their roles and responsibilities, the institution adopt the following strategies in training, retraining and motivating for attaining faculty empowerment.

Table 1 : Strategies adopted by the institution for faculty empowerment

S. No.	Problem	Strategies adopted	Areas of Training, Retraining and motivation	Resulting empowerment
1	Language & Fluency	Frequent use	Communication	Improved ability in communication
2	Deficiency in comprehension	Increased reading	Knowledge	Enhanced competence in imparting knowledge
3	Poor Presentation	Providing know how	Skill	Effective presentation
4	Effective Judgment	Providing guidelines	Evaluation	Fair assessment
5	Strained	Group activities	Team work	Collaboration and

	interpersonal relation			synergy
6	Lack of sensitivity to student difficulties	Increased interactions	Counseling	Better student-teacher relation.
7	Inadequate use of technology	Support facility	Technology adoption	Use of teaching aids & electronic media for effective teaching
8	Negative thinking	Re-orientation	Attitude	Positive thinker
9	Stagnation	Provoking analytical thinking	Advancement of research	More publications & contributions
10	Challenges in effective teaching	Competition for excellence	Teaching Innovation	Adoption of creative thinking and improvement in teaching methods.

Details on the Performance Appraisal System:

The details of the performance appraisal system to evaluate and encourage the staff members in their improvement are as follows :

- A. At the end of each semester, a filled-in feedback form will be collected from the students about the faculty engaging the class, which evaluates about teaching methodology, creativity and level of understanding.
- B. The self-appraisal form will be filled in by the staff by providing the details of teaching, results obtained in internal examination and varsity examinations, books and papers published, conferences, seminars, workshops, training programmes, research, consultancy and academic administration carried out during the academic year.
- C. In the appraisal form, the Head of the Institute gives the feedback about the overall performance of the faculty on the basis of the information provided by the staff members in their self-appraisal form and also through regular presentations where the faculty contributes the information and ideas in the improvement.

The institution utilizes such evaluations to improve teaching/research capability of the faculty. The information helps the faculty to gain insights for improvement. The following decisions were taken in the light of the review of the performance appraisal report.

- (1) Enhance competency through strengthening knowledge in the subject.
- (2) Introduce variety of teaching methods suited to the requirements of the subject.
- (3) Increase interaction with the students and promote participation in the learning.
- (4) Develop accessibility to the students outside the class.
- (5) Prepare adequately prior to the classes.
- (6) Ensure syllabus completion time.
- (7) Maintain regularity in conducting classes.
- (8) Adopt better presentation skills.
- (9) Time bound publications to be produced.
- (10) Concentrate on research projects
- (11) Present papers in conferences and workshops
- (12) Contribute to the specific events organized by the institution.
- (13) Participate in faculty development programs.
- (14) Write books, monographs etc.
- (15) Review research papers/ books.
- (16) Involve in course material development.
- (17) Plan and schedule classes.
- (18) Learn proper academic record keeping.
- (19) Encourage assignments/tutorials.
- (20) Develop dependability.
- (21) Maintain regularity and punctuality.
- (22) Display sincerity, Integrity, and maturity.

- (23) Develop better evaluation practices.
- (24) Acquire higher qualifications.
- (25) Involve in admission of students.
- (26) Deliver expert lecture at as invited talks.
- (27) Chair technical sessions.
- (28) Win recognition in professional bodies.
- (29) Receive honours in industry/community service.
- (30) Obtain better peer group evaluation.
- (31) Better advisor & communicator to guardians.

This is communicated to the appropriate stake holders in faculty meetings with management. Performance budgeting is incorporated as a core planning activity by the institution for informed decision making.

Welfare Schemes Available for Teaching and Non-teaching Staff :

The various welfare schemes available for teaching and non-teaching staff and the percentage of staff availed such benefits in the last four years in Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, is given in table 2.

Table 2 : Utilization of various welfare schemes by staff members

S. No.	Welfare scheme	Percentage of staff availed the benefit in terms need
1	Drinking water	100 %
2	Rest room	100 %
3	Canteen	60 %
4	First Aid	10 %
5	Proper workplace seating	100 %
6	Laptops for faculty	80 %
7	Blazers for faculty	100 %
8	Health Insurance	100 %
9	Privileged leave	100 %
10	Vacation for the faculty	100 %
11	Scholarship for the children of staff	100 %

12	Preference for spouse in employment	100 %
13	Concessional fee for admission to courses for dependent of staff.	100 %
14.	Admission to children of staff sister institutions	100 %
15	Concessional medical facility for staff in Srinivas hospital.	100 %
16	Physiotherapy and blood bank services.	100 %
17	Maternity Leave for women employees	100 %
18	Subsidized canteen facility for staff member	100 %
19	Free Uniforms of non-teaching staff	100 %
20	Car Parking facility	100%
21	Round the clock security	100 %
22	Bank & Stationary shop inside the premises	60 %
23	Free transport in college bus	30 %
24	Lift facility for staff	100 %
25	Free dairy as new year compliment	100 %
26	Games facility	20 %

Measures Taken by the Institution for Attracting and Retaining Eminent Faculty:

The institution has taken number of measures for attracting and retaining eminent faculty to improve its service quality. Some of them are :

- (1) Good infrastructural facilities and positive work environment are offered to the faculty members..
- (2) Encouragement is given to the faculty members in pursuing research and consultation activities.
- (3) Competitive remuneration is offered for all levels of faculty.
- (4) Opportunity is provided to participate in programmes organized by the institute.
- (5) Training and Faculty development programmes are organized for the professional development of the faculty.
- (6) Encouragement in presenting papers in conference, seminars etc. organized by other institutions.
- (7) Various welfare facilities mentioned in above are provided to the faculty members.

- (8) Opportunity to accompany the students in foreign tour free of cost.
- (9) Providing autonomy and freedom in work.

Conclusion:

1. The institution takes sustained interest in recruitment and promotion aspects of its employees.
2. The institution adheres to GOI/ State Govt. policies on recruitment (access, equity, gender sensitivity and physically disabled).
3. The institution has an effective welfare mechanism for teaching and non-teaching staff.
4. The institution ensures transparent use of Performance Appraisal Reports.
5. The institution conducts programmes to enhance the competency of its staff.
6. Performance budgeting is a core planning activity used by the institution for informed decision making.
7. Effective welfare mechanisms of the institutions are available to its staff.
8. The institution conducts programme for professional development of its staff.

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